

Student-Perceived Service Quality in Management Science MS, PhD Programs of Tier 1 Business Schools in Karachi

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 01, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Perceived Service Quality, SERVQUAL, Higher Education and MS/PhD Program</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5391842</p>	<p><i>The contemporary academic environment, marked by the marketization of education, have been observing adoption of the practices and concepts originating from the business world. An example of marketization of education is the adoption of the concept of measurement of service quality which is already established in the business world, and now increasingly gaining recognition in the academia as well. This research is an attempt to evaluate service quality in Management Sciences programs using students' perception. A sample of MS, PhD program of Tier 1 private sector business schools operating in Karachi. A modified version of the standard SERVQUAL instrument that was previously authorized by a PhD faculty member and three students of the MS program, was used to collect data from the students of this program, both former and current. The findings of this study outlined a gap between expectations and perceptions of students in all the five dimensions, known as: assurance, tangibility, empathy, reliability, and responsiveness of service quality. A detailed analysis of the data revealed that the campus facilities, access to academic and research resources, consultation time, and access to advisors are some of the areas, where the university administrators should be focusing their attention more. Although, this study is not rigorous because of short time horizon and low response rate, nevertheless, the study has attempted to explore into some of the service quality-related problems the management sciences faculty has currently been experiencing. Moreover, the gap model discussed in this study may prove to be a valuable tool for the administrators to enhance the service quality of the faculty..</i></p>

Introduction

Contemporary research has provided for conclusive evidence on how to identify product dimensions and perform their measurements; this is primarily due to the tangibility of their nature. However, the inquiries regarding measurement of service quality has not met with definite answers. Facing the dilemma that a service cannot be measured using uni-dimensional construct similar to height, weights, and others, researchers have obviously been struggling to devise its measurable dimensions since long without considerable success. Nonetheless, because of the influence of quality-related work initiated by Deming and some other researchers, now the qualitative and intangible constructs are often being employed to quantify and portion out service quality.

In the current world, higher educational institutions increasingly face a competitive environment. With more globalization, availability of sophisticated technology, deregulation, and other regulatory intervention universities are pressed hard on reshaping their resources to match market dynamics. Majority of the universities, therefore, are now seeking to adopt student-centric approaches in order to treat their students as customers, and hence ensure their survival and growth. Therefore, many of the primary activities performed by the universities, though very different in several dimensions, are being compared to the similar activities performed in the business arena. Therefore, various theoretic paradigms and different tools developed in the world of business have commonly been borrowed by the academic industry in order to assess higher education. Fundamentally a complex service, education requires multi-faceted construct representing the perspectives of a variety of stakeholders; but still, some of the distinctive service components like 'service quality' are considered similar to any other service providing entity.

Several studies have been conducted through the standard SERVQUAL instrument in order to calculate the service quality in several areas specific to education. In the contemporary academic environment there is also a high demand for student-centric approach to education especially in the developed countries.

This study is an attempt to evaluate service quality in Management Science MS, PhD program of Tier 1 business schools in Karachi. The primary objective of this paper is to discover the extent to which MS and PhD programs in the field of management sciences satisfy students' expectations of service quality. For this, the

measurement of service quality is performed through students' perception in accordance with the SERVQUAL model.

Statement of the Problem

Operating in a highly competitive environment, higher education institutes, are fast adapting to the needs of their students. A positive students' perception, therefore, goes a long way in enhancing the image of a higher education institution. Accordingly, these institutions attempt to take several synchronized actions to modify students' perception in their favor. Indeed, image or reputation fosters growth by attracting by attracting sufficient number of students. Therefore, it is critical that students should evaluate the academic environment at the university, faculty, and programs levels. The programs such as MS and PhD in Management Sciences have already been recognized in the marketplace, however, they are still quite young. Therefore, it is important at this stage to find out the level of expectation gap for these programs. This exercise will provide important information to management, in the form of customers' perception of quality of programs, which they may incorporate in their management information system in order to apply suitable interventions to fill the identified gaps.

Purpose of Study

Study aims to evaluate service quality in post-graduate programs offered by faculty of management sciences at private sector business schools in Pakistan.

Objectives of Study

The primary objective of this research is to find out whether students are satisfied with the post-graduate program offered by faculty of management science in terms of dimensions such as tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness of service quality as recognized by the adapted version of SERVQUAL.

Scope

Scope of this study is confined to Karachi and MS and PhD program in management science. Academic programs in social science, computer science, and engineering domain are not within the scope of this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service

Services being intangible are inherently different from products, and constitute any action or performance by one person to another Kotler (2003). An assessment of a products is generally based on objective criteria including durability, performance, and size, which cannot be completely applied to assess a service. As services are intangible, therefore, customers's evaluative judgment is required to assess their quality Parasuraman et al. (1991). Tangibility is not the only attribute that creates distinction between a product and a service; there are other important attributes such as inability to separate production and consumption, heterogeneity, and perishability which also create distinction between the two " (Mukhtar et al., 2015). Parsuraman et al (1991) argues that that these three attributes must be adequately examined before any attempt is made to evaluate the service quality. A close examination is much needed in the case of a service because, whereas a product quality can be measured by objective indicators of performance, features, and durability, the quality of a service may not be similarly evaluated as it exists only in customers' perceptions (Mashene, 2019).

Service Quality

An existing movement measures the qualitative factors between disciplines varying from Human Resources Management to Strategic Management. As a result, not only subjects like finance but other distinctive courses lend easily to some quantitative criteria that were traditionally recognized as being qualitative. This is reflected from the fact that these so-called qualitative courses have progressed towards adopting performance matrices which are trending towards quantification and measurement. Nevertheless, the total evaluation of services possesses another challenge. Randheer (2015) claims that service quality is a differentiator itself. He also doubts about its discrete nature and further claims that evaluation of service quality requires continual practice. Accordingly, he argues similar to Parasuraman et al (1991) that service quality is an evaluative process which is experienced by the consumers over the course of a period of time; but if that is the reason, how would a person quantify such a concentrated construct?. Although, Randheer (2015) pointed out the continuous feature of service quality, Azam (2018) put forwards that, "conceptions of quality are socially constructed, differ in different periods and vary according to their political and cultural context."

Service Quality Gap Model

Kavitha (2015), in her study, recommends the higher education institutions to employ The Gap Model of service quality that has been derived from SERVQUAL. Service quality addresses the quality of ongoing relationship between the customers and service providers. The gap model discusses the difference between the expected value of the service and the perceived value of the service received by the customer.

According to the Gaps Model, expectations of service quality can be considered as subjective while perceptions of service quality are findings about a service performance (Parasuraman et al, 1991). However, expectations are said to keep changing, they might increase or decrease, on the basis of different criteria (Hassan & Yousuf,

2015). Hassan and Yousof (2015) further claims that confirmations/disconfirmations process feed and support the functioning of the Gaps Model. They added that: expectations always prove more beneficial as it produces reference through which experiences of the customers are judged. They claim that consumers' opinions are formed, about a product or service, before they even experience it. Moreover, they also explained the factors which influence the formation of customers' expectations, which are: demographic profile of the customers, word of mouth communication, personal needs, previous experience, and external communication to customers, etc". Ultimately, it does not matter how these expectations might have been formed but they do factor in the actual calculation, of the service quality, as performed by the customer. It is necessary that a customer has multiple experiences specific to the delivery of a service, and only then they can differentiate between their expectations and perceptions. It is true that customer's perception is established if the performance and the expectations overlap. Kavitha also negated if performance exceeds expectations and expectations exceed performance.

SERVQUAL v. SERVPERV

Different scholars developed different measurement tools in order to measure the service quality however SERVQUAL is exemplary. Similarly, a few academicians have created their own tools to quantify service quality for the higher education institutions; out of these, the instruments such as SERVQUAL and SERVPERV stand out from the rest. Moreover, some modified and highly effective variants of SERVQUAL were also discussed and written about in the literature. The first version of SERVQUAL featured ten dimensions, however, the reduction in dimensions continued to occur to the point where now it features only five dimensions. The five dimensions currently used are: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The mechanism is built on the Gaps model, which measure the service quality based on gaps between customer perceptions and expectations. Several scholars have also argued about these dimensions being contextual (Buttle, 1996). Randheer (2015) suggested that culture contributes to outline the process of consumer perception of the elements of quality. Different Scholars argue that a service environment is very important and an instrument should be modified accordingly in consideration of the study's context. However, SERVQUAL has been widely recognized and is still used effectively in a valid and reliable fashion across multiple service environments. Rahimi et al. (2015) also used SERVQUAL and Kano Model in order to measure service quality at Shiraz University of Medical Sciences.

Offshoot of the SERVQUAL scale is known as SERVPERF because it is based solely on the perception component (Adil et al., 2013). As mentioned above, SERVQUAL operates at a disconfirmation paradigm, on the other hand SERVPERV operates only on perception. Thus, the measurement approaches used by these two scales are different. One scale considers both expectations and perceptions, whereas another scale considers only perception. Therefore, actually, the cause of difference is the construct of expectations (Rodrigues et al., 2011). "Educational institutions that are willing to embrace student perceptions will gain more than institutions that do not" (Gopalakrishnan 2014). In contrast, Keszei&Kenesei (2014) projected a substitutive attitude to measure service quality in higher educations by using SERVQUAL scale. Here, they suggest that measuring "disconfirmation directly compared to ideal and minimal requirements of students."

Service Quality in Higher Education

Ansary et al. (2014) recommends, "Tertiary institutions should measure their services rendered to the students and attempt to improve." Ansary stresses: low perception regarding that of service quality results in the decrease of customers' base. "Global competition has brought to the fore the critical importance of quality education, and the demand for new competencies in today's information society" (Alani et al 2015). "The quality in higher education has a direct impact on student acquiring the right skills, which helps him in employability" (Randheer, 2015).

Several researches have been conducted on a global scale to measure the multiple elements of service quality in the higher education environment. According to Alani et al. (2015), higher education institutions (HEIs) are increasingly being scrutinized as is done in the business world, leading to a positive direction and focus to the quality of higher education. "Two primary methods of quality exist: quality assurance and total quality management. Almost no Pakistani university has been able to adopt total quality management in its true spirit, however, due to pressure from the Pakistan Higher Education Commission (HEC), majority of them have started to maintain rudimentary quality assurance (QA) systems to meet the requirements of regulatory agencies. Quality assurance is classified into two types: external and internal (Alani, Yasir and Hamdan, 2015), where the plans for regulators are considered external.

Ravindran & Kalpana (2012) stressed that, students normally expect a brilliant service from higher education institutions. Choudhury (2015) claims: service quality is a multidimensional complex construct and its dimensions are contextual. Nonetheless, Ewell as cited in Singh & Kumar (2014), showed concern by stating that it may be disastrous to strictly apply the thought of consumer service in higher-education; particularly, when the only performance criteria is students' satisfaction. In other words, the precise purposes of education is to be appreciated and the interests of a diversified group of stakeholders connected with higher education.

Overview of Higher Education in Pakistan

Pakistan is a unique example of a muslim majority country. There, universities operating on the so-called western models have been running for decades. But this modern higher education is mixed with medieval methodologies adopted commonly by the universities located across the country. During the colonial period, the western modeled university continues to some extent faithful to the spirit of flawless scientific investigation, freedom of expression, but over the course of time these institutions came under the influence of people who were the product of medieval thought. This medieval concept creates discrimination based on religion based on exclusivity, gender, class, linguistic group, sectarianism, etc., providing ideological comfort by an affinity with conspiracy theories and a reduction in freedom of expression in support of religious doctrine. As such, it is difficult to say that a university is a place of learning.

As a result, innovation and creativity have actually been stifled, as evidenced by Pakistan's low ranking in new patents and new process applications. Although Pakistanis have performed well in Western institutions, Pakistan has made little contribution to pure science, social science research, and economic decision-making in the past several decades. Many scholars have cited the inadequacy of the content of social sciences in the curriculum as the reason for this failure.

Another obvious issue with of so-called modern universities in Pakistan is the dogmatic contentdelivery atmosphere, which contributes towards adoption of passive learning styles. Absolute memorization of the content remains commonplace, and the system does not instill the ability to critically analyze problems or prompt students to develop problem-solving skills. However, things have improved tremendously with Higher Education Commission (HEC) playing its active role with the help of much financial assistance from the United States. In 2002, the Presidential Decree changed the name of the College Scholarship Committee, the highest formal institution, to the Powerful Higher Education Committee, and along with it emerged much-needed funding. New universities came into being which rose to 163 in number (HEC, website), and scholarships were provided generously to students and teachers to obtain certificates abroad, and with the help of the American Agency for International Assistance for Pakistan, the largest country's start-up -specific Fulbright scholarship program in history. At present, just over 26% of all faculty and staff in Pakistani universities have PhD degrees, and more than 1.1 million students are enrolled in higher education institutions. Despite these enviable statistics, some experts claim that corruption is eroding the academic system, and publishing research papers has become a digital game (Halai, 2013)

SERVQUAL Studies in Pakistan

Unlike India (Chatterjee et al., 2009) where many studies have already employed SERVQUAL, only a few studies have implemented SERVQUAL in Pakistan as a measurement tool to quantify the quality of services of educational institutions. Higher IES. As far as the authors of this study know, the only important research using the SERVQUAL model was carried out by Mukhtar et al. (2015) who compared the service quality between public and private universities in operation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research follows a positivist philosophy and uses a deductive method. The research is mainly based on cross-sectional data analysis; however, an exception is when we collect the same data from a business school in two waves over three years. Uses a unique cross-sectional data collection method through surveys distributed electronically via links. Use SPSS software for descriptive and reasoned statistical analysis.

Method and Procedure

Through an in-depth study of the existing literature on service quality, the method and location of the research is determined. Current science provides several tools to measure service quality, but after carefully evaluating the pros and cons of research, considering the skill level of the researchers and many other limitations, SERVQUAL and the accompanying GAPS model appear to be the best choice.

Therefore, an adapted version of SERVQUAL used in the early days of Shiraz University in Iran was selected, and its content and surface effectiveness were enhanced by an experienced member of the doctoral faculty and three master's students from the program. Subsequently, his suggestion was adopted and the revised version was published on the Internet as a Google doc. After that, the link to the file was sent to the target group and they were asked to fill it out. The response is compiled into a worksheet with a time stamp, and the worksheet is converted to an Excel worksheet in the required format. Finally, import the data in the Excel spreadsheet into SPSS software for descriptive and reasoning statistical analysis.

Population and Target Frame

The object of this study are all students who have enrolled in master's and doctorate courses since its inception. After obtaining the necessary permits, the university provided contact information via email for all students enrolled in the program.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Since the full sampling frame is only 980, it was decided that the census method is more appropriate. Also, the response rate is expected to be low. Therefore, the link was sent to all email addresses, but only 148 former and current students took the time to complete the questionnaire..

Instrument Selection

After carefully evaluating the research goals, limitations, and arguments for and against various measurement tools, the research used an adapted version of SERVQUAL. This particular tool was previously used in a study by Rahimi et al., Shiraz Medical University uses the Servqual and Kano model to determine the quality of educational services. (2015). This particular instrument had 30 questions designed to measure service quality via its five recognized dimensions; 4 questions exploring tangibles, 5 questions exploring reliability, followed by 11, 5, and 5 questions for assurance, empathy, and responsiveness dimensions respectively. The instrument was further refined by soliciting the feedback of one PhD professor of marketing having extensive experience in quality-related issues and three MS students of the program. All three have business degrees and considerable work experience. An attempt was also made to contextualize the Iranian study instrument's language to the research in hand. This exercise was taken to create content and face validity of the instrument. Consequently, the final instrument of this study attempts to measure service quality via 28 questions, each for five dimensions of perception and expectation. Besides, these 28 questions, there were some questions, which were demographic in nature as well as two more open-ended questions soliciting the feedback of the respondents.

During the iterative vetting process with four experts, the construct of tangible was reduced to 3 questions as one question exploring the external beauty of items used by teachers was dropped. Similarly, putting promises into action was dropped out of the reliability construct, thus leaving only 4 questions for it. The experts also reduced the number of questions for the assurance construct from 11 to 9, however, students' preparation for future jobs by providing them theoretical and practical training in the school was bifurcated into two questions. Likewise, two questions exploring reputation and quality separately were merged into a single question. The construct empathy, though has the same number of questions but assigning appropriate, related homework was bifurcated into two questions and suitable performance of the whole university staff towards students was dropped together. For the construct of responsiveness, 7 questions were created out of the original 5 questions as two questions were split into 4 questions. Likert scale measured all the variables, using a five-pointer, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

Variables

The research mainly focuses on the five dimensions of service quality listed by SERVQUAL, which are tangibility, reliability, security, empathy, and responsiveness.

Hypotheses

The Gaps Model operates on measured changes in perceptions and expectations in the various constructs of service quality. An ideal situation has no difference between the values of perception of a given service quality dimension and its expectations. Thus, the following five hypotheses were developed outlining the same situation:

H1: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the tangibles dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

$$\underline{\text{Mean Perception Tangibles}-\text{Mean Expectation Tangibles}=0}$$

H2: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the reliability dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

$$\underline{\text{Mean Perception Reliability}-\text{Mean Expectation Reliability}=0}$$

H3: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the assurance dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

$$\underline{\text{Mean Perception Assurance}-\text{Mean Expectation Assurance}=0}$$

H4: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the empathy dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

$$\underline{\text{Mean Perception Empathy}-\text{Mean Expectation Empathy}=0}$$

H5: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the responsiveness dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

$$\underline{\text{Mean Perception Responsiveness}-\text{Mean Expectation Responsiveness}=0}$$

Plan of Analysis

Initially, four academic experts verified the content and face validity of the adapted version of the standard SERVQUAL questionnaire. After data collection, Cronbach's α was used to verify the reliability and structure of the questionnaire. The normality of the data is assessed, and then the paired sample is tested to accept or reject the hypothesis. Subsequently, a one-sample t test was performed to see whether students are generally satisfied with the various dimensions of service quality, and a test value derived from the Likert scale = 2 was established. Based on the analysis of the gap between expectations and perceptions of each variable, and the service quality structure listed by SERVQUAL recommendations have been made.

Software for Analysis

SPSS 23.0 is used to conduct descriptive and inferential statistical analyses of quantitative data collected through the primary data collection method of a survey questionnaire.

FINDINGS

Total number of 148 respondents participated in the survey from two of the top-tier private business schools in Karachi. More than 75% of the respondents were from University 1 which included 58 respondents from 2016. University 2 students were made part of the research in 2019.

Table 1

Respondents profile

Variables	Type	Frequency (n=148)	%
Gender	Male	70	47.3
	Female	78	52.7
Age	Less than 25K	17	11.5
	26-60K	37	25.0
	61-100K	46	31.1
	101-160K	27	18.2
	160K and above	21	14.2
University	University 1	113	76.4
	University 2	35	23.6
Current Profession	Academic	84	56.8
	Non-academic	64	43.2
Program	MS	79	53.4
	PhD	69	46.6

Table 2 shows the reliability of the structure. It can be seen from the PP chart that the data is normally distributed; therefore, many statistical inference procedures are applicable. The instrument was found to be highly reliable, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.923. Similarly, with one exception, a single construct was found to be reliable and its value exceeded 0.7.

Finally, comparing the expected approach with the perception of individual projects and structures allows us to perform a gap analysis, which shows that there are gaps in almost all the service quality variables.

The following is the calculated average of each variable in the questionnaire:

Table 2

Reliability of Constructs

Construct Name	Cronbach Alpha
Tangibles expectation	.857
Tangibles perception	.708
Reliable expectation	.917
Reliable perception	.889
Assurance expectation	.947
Assurance perception	.933
Empathy expectation	.718
Empathy perception	.712
Responsiveness expectation	.942
Responsiveness perception	.927

H1: There is no difference in students' perceptions and expectations of the tangible dimensions of the services provided by the program.

In other words:

H1: Mean Perception Tangibles-Mean Expectation Tangibles=0

Table 3

Mean comparisons of expectations and perceptions

Construct Name	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Gap	t	Sig
Tangibles expectation	2.482	1.185	-0.223	-2.330	0.021
Tangibles perception	2.705	1.005			

According to the results shown in table 3, the mean difference is -0.233 and *t* is significant as the *p*-value is less than 0.05. Hypothesis 1 is not supported as a significant difference was noted between perception tangible and expectation tangible.

H2: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the reliability dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

H2: Mean Perception Reliability-Mean Expectation Reliability=0

Table 4

Mean comparisons of expectations and perceptions

Construct Name	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Gap	t	Sig
Reliability expectation	2.480	1.118	-0.522	-6.061	0.000
Reliability perception	3.002	1.173			

According to the results shown in Table 4, the average difference is 0.522 and *t* is significant because the *p*-value is less than 0.001. Hypothesis 2 is not supported because there is a significant difference between perceived and expected reliability.

H3: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the assurance dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

H3: Mean Perception Reliability-Mean Expectation Reliability=0

Table 5

Mean comparisons of expectations and perceptions

Construct Name	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Gap	t	Sig
Assurance expectation	2.537	1.085	-0.522	-5.841	0.000
Assurance perception	3.088	1.114			

According to the results shown in table 5, the mean difference is -0.522 and *t* is significant as the *p*-value is less than 0.001. Hypothesis 3 is not supported as a significant difference was noted between perception assurance and expectation assurance.

H4: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the empathy dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

H4: Mean Perception Empathy-Mean Expectation Empathy=0

Table 6

Mean comparisons of expectations and perceptions

Construct Name	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Gap	T	Sig
Empathy expectation	2.646	0.844	-0.521	-6.580	0.000
Empathy perception	3.166	0.920			

According to the results shown in table 6, the mean difference is -0.521 and *t* is significant as the *p*-value is less than 0.001. Hypothesis 4 is not supported as a significant difference was noted between perception empathy and expectation empathy.

H5: There will be no difference between students' perceptions and expectations regarding the responsiveness dimension of the services rendered by the program. In other words:

H5: Mean Perception Responsiveness-Mean Expectation Responsiveness=0

Table 7

Mean comparisons of expectations and perceptions

Construct Name	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean Gap	T	Sig
Responsiveness expectation	2.557	1.128	-0.661	-6.844	0.000
Responsiveness perception	3.218	1.150			

According to the results shown in table 7, the mean difference is -0.661 and *t* is significant as the *p*-value is less than 0.001. Hypothesis 5 is not supported as a significant difference was noted between perception responsiveness and expectation responsiveness.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusions

Since there is a gap between the expectations and perceptions of students on the five dimensions of service quality, managers must pay attention to the service quality of the project. For example, the tangible and responsive dimensions have relatively large differences in average expectations and average perceptions. In addition, there is no separate space for master and doctoral students, so this result is somewhat expected.

Findings & Implications

Administrative and financial resources are often limited; therefore, managers must focus on those areas where expectations have the greatest gaps. For example, the tangibility and responsiveness dimensions have a relatively large gap between expectation and perception, although the difference between each dimension of service quality and the average is very close. In addition, a comprehensive analysis of the gaps in individual projects shows that physical infrastructure, access to research resources, databases, off-campus links, teacher consultation and the availability of consultants are some of the areas that require immediate attention from managers. Students seem to be generally dissatisfied with the service quality of the project. Almost every aspect of the service quality provides the management department with opportunities for further improvement. Surprisingly, the students' evaluation of the perceived reality of the assigned tasks was lower than they expected.

Limitations and Future Directions

The study is not complex in its design as we wanted to kick off the conversation regarding quality within the wider ambit of the philosophical debate whether higher education providers can be considered as service providers. This very notion with neoliberal moorings violates many traditions associated with the ideals of university education as understood by traditional academicians and administrators. However, now higher education institutions have metamorphosed into a blend of the traditional model and modern accountable-managerial model due to the encroachment of myriad forces, which are at play in the greater society.

The study is based on analysis of primarily cross-sectional data; however, one exception is when we collected the same data from one business school in two waves three years apart. In 2016 58 respondents participated, then another second wave of data was collected in 2019 when 90 students filled out our questionnaire. The comparable data from another institution was collected in 2019 alone. However, due to the low response rate, the relative strength of data itself eliminates the possibility of identifying causation and obviously its direction. The low response rate and the consequently limited analysis put into question many of the assumptions of validity; however, we did our level best to present our findings within the contours of reliability and validity.

This research is based on the design of the survey; therefore, the statement about the relationship is only valid within the limits of the design permission. Research is quantitative; perhaps in the future, these structures should be explored through qualitative research that triangulates data and its results. Quantitative research to capture what is essentially an attitude or satisfaction is problematic. In addition, performance-based competition models can also be explored. Of course, the scale can be refined and updated to capture the richness of the structure.

A research using a larger sample may be conducted, where the research instrument is further refined with the help of a focus group or a pilot study. Moreover, the cultural dimension could be included as part of the service quality as substantial level of literature suggests that culture is an important factor contributing to the evaluation of service quality. Finally, a comparative study could be conducted featuring various academic domains. Similarly, the geographic scope of the study could be enlarged to include other cities.

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